

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF PARACETAMOL AND DICLOFENAC SODIUM BY USING RP-HPLC IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

The current investigation was pointed at developing and progressively validating novel, simple, responsive and stable RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous measurement of active pharmaceutical ingredients of Diclofenac Sodium and Paracetamol. The chromatographic strategy utilized Kromasil C-18 column of dimensions (150x4.6 mm, 3.5 μ m), using isocratic elution with a mobile phase of acetonitrile and Ammonium acetate of pH-2.5 adjusted with OPA (20:80). A flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, injection volume of 10 μ l and a detector wavelength of 278 nm utilizing the PDA detector were given in the instrumental settings. LOD and LOQ for the active ingredient were established with respect to test concentration. The calibration chart plotted was linear with a regression coefficient of $R^2 > 0.999$, means the linearity was within the limit. Specificity, linearity, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness were determined as a part of method validation and the results were found to be within the acceptable range. Validation of the proposed method was carried out according to an international conference on harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The proposed method to be fast, simple, feasible and affordable in assay condition. During stability tests, it can be used for routine analysis of production samples and to verify the quality of drug samples during stability studies.

Key words: Diclofenac Sodium, Paracetamol, RP-HPLC, Development, Validation.

INTRODUCTION

Paracetamol, or **acetaminophen**, is a non-opioid analgesic and antipyretic [1] agent used to treat fever and mild to moderate pain [2]. It is a widely available over-the-counter drug sold under various brand names, including **Tylenol** and **Panadol**. Paracetamol relieves pain in both acute mild migraine [3] and episodic tension headache [4]. At a standard dose, paracetamol slightly reduces fever, though it is inferior to ibuprofen in that respect and the benefits of its use for fever are unclear, particularly in the context of fever of viral origins [5]. The aspirin/paracetamol/caffeine combination also helps with both conditions when the pain

is mild and is recommended as a first-line treatment for them. Paracetamol is effective for post-surgical pain, but is inferior to ibuprofen for this purpose. The paracetamol/ibuprofen combination increases the drugs' potency and is superior to either drug alone. The pain relief paracetamol provides in osteoarthritis [6, 7] is small and clinically insignificant. Evidence supporting its use in low back pain [8, 9], cancer pain [10], and neuropathic pain [11, 12] is insufficient. In the short term, paracetamol is safe and effective when used as directed. Short term adverse effects are uncommon and similar to ibuprofen, but paracetamol is typically safer than nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [13, 14] for long-term use. Paracetamol is also often used in patients who cannot tolerate NSAIDs like ibuprofen. Chronic consumption of paracetamol may result in a drop in hemoglobin level, indicating possible gastrointestinal bleeding [15], and abnormal liver function tests.

Diclofenac, sold under the brand name **Voltaren** among others, is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) used to treat pain and inflammatory diseases such as gout [16]. It can be taken orally (swallowed by mouth), inserted rectally as a suppository, injected intramuscularly, injected intravenously, applied to the skin topically, or through eye drops [17]. Improvements in pain last up to eight hours. It is also available as the fixed-dose combination diclofenac/misoprostol (Arthrotec) to help protect the stomach; however, proton pump inhibitors [19] such as omeprazole are typically first-line since they are at least as effective as misoprostol, but with better tolerability [20]. Common side effects include abdominal pain, gastrointestinal bleeding, nausea, dizziness, headache, and swelling. Serious side effects may include heart disease, stroke, kidney problems, and stomach ulceration [21]. Use is not recommended in the third trimester of pregnancy. It is likely safe during breastfeeding. Diclofenac is believed to work by decreasing the production of prostaglandins, like other drugs in this class.

The aim of the study is to estimate the pharma ingredients Diclofenac Sodium and Paracetamol by using RP-HPLC.

Fig. 1: Structure of (A) Paracetamol and (B) Diclofenac Sodium

1. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Chemicals: Acetonitrile (HPLC-grade), water was purchased from Merck India Ltd, Mumbai, India. APIs and samples of Paracetamol, Diclofenac Sodium were procured from Zydus Cadila, Ahmedabad. Ortho phosphoric acid, ammonium acetate of AR grade were purchased from local vendour.

2.2 The Instrumentation: Waters Alliance e-2695 high performance liquid chromatography monitored with empower 2.0 data handling system was used for this study.

2.3 Method optimization: To optimize the chromatographic conditions, different ratios of acetate, formic acid buffers and the acetonitrile in the mobile phase with isocratic mode was tested. However the mobile phase composition was modified at each trial to enhance the resolution and also to achieve acceptable retention time. Finally Ammonium acetate of pH-2.5 adjusted with ortho phosphoric acid buffer and acetonitrile with isocratic elution was selected because it results in a greater response of active pharmacy ingredients. During the optimization of the method various stationary phases such as C₈, C₁₈ and phenyl columns were tested. From these trials the peak shape was relatively good with Kromasil C-18 column of (150 x 4.6mm, 3.5 µm) with a PDA detector. The mobile phase flow rate has been done at 1.0 ml/min in order to obtain enough sensitivity. By using above conditions we get retention time of Paracetamol was about 2.914 min and Diclofenac Sodium was 3.465 min. According to ICH guidelines, the method established was validated.

2.4 Validation procedure

The analytical parameters such as system suitability, precision, specificity, accuracy, linearity, robustness, LOD, LOQ, forced degradation and stability were validated according to ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines.

2.5 Preparation of buffer: 7.7 g of ammonium acetate was dissolved in 1 lt of HPLC grade water and adjust its pH-2.5 with ortho phosphoric acid. Filter this solution using 0.45 µ filter paper.

2.6 Chromatographic conditions: The HPLC analysis was performed on reverse phase HPLC system with isocratic elution mode using a mobile phase of acetonitrile (20%) and ammonium acetate of pH-2.5 adjusted with ortho phosphoric acid (80%) and Kromasil C-18 (150x4.6 mm, 3.5 µm) column with a flow rate of 1.0 ml /min.

2.7 Diluent: Acetonitrile and water (50:50) was used as diluent.

2.8 Preparation of the standard solution: Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Diclofenac Sodium and 65 mg of Paracetamol working standards into a 10ml volumetric flask, add 7ml of diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make up to the mark with diluent. This is the standard stock solution. Take 1 ml of standard stock and transferred it into 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with diluents.

2.9 Preparation of the sample solution: Sample solution containing 650µg/ml of Paracetamol and 100µg/ml of Diclofenac Sodium was prepared by dissolving 84.8 mg of Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium sample (label claim 325mg of Paracetamol, 50mg of Diclofenac Sodium) in 10 ml of mobile phase solvent blend. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main analytical challenge during development of a new method was to separate active pharma ingredients. In order to provide a good performance the chromatographic conditions were optimized.

3.1 System suitability: In System suitability injecting standard solution and reported USP tailing and plate count values are tabulated in table 1 and the standard chromatogram was shown in figure 2.

Table 1: Results of system suitability

System suitability parameter	Acceptance criteria	Drug name	
		Paracetamol	Diclofenac Sodium
USP Plate Count	NLT 2000	6682	3015
USP Tailing	NMT 2.0	1.08	0.96
USP Resolution	NLT 2.0	-	8.56
% RSD	NMT 2.0	0.21	0.36

Fig. 2: Chromatogram of Standard

3.2 Specificity: In this test method placebo and standard solutions were analyzed individually to examine the interference. The below figure shows that the active ingredients were well separated from blank and their excipients and there was no interference of placebo with the principal peak. Hence the method is specific.

Fig. 3: Chromatogram of blank

3.3 Linearity: The area of the linearity peak versus different concentrations has been evaluated for Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium as 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150 percent dilutions respectively. Linearity was performed in the range of 162.5-975 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Paracetamol and 25-150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Diclofenac Sodium. The correlation coefficient achieved greater than 0.999 for all.

Table 2: Linearity results

S. No	Paracetamol		Diclofenac Sodium	
	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Area	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Area
1	162.50	681124	25.00	100547
2	325.00	1325605	50.00	203659
3	487.50	2047242	75.00	305623
4	650.00	2660358	100.00	401526
5	812.50	3296123	125.00	504213
6	975.00	3884515	150.00	598745
The correlation coefficient		0.99964		0.99993
Slope		4004.02		4002.05
Intercept		33035.00		1891.07

A

B

Fig. 4: Calibration plot of (A) Paracetamol and (B) Diclofenac Sodium

3.4 Accuracy: Three kinds of concentration levels of 80, 100, and 120 percent at a specified limit were used in this process to assess the accuracy of this particular method. The developed method was found to be highly accurate and reliable. The recovery percentages were given in table 3.

Table 3: Results of accuracy of (A) Paracetamol and (B) Diclofenac Sodium

A

Level (%)	Sample peak area	Amount of standard added (mg)	Amount recovered	% Recovery ± SD, %RSD (n = 3)
50	1322458	32.5	32.745	100.3 ± 0.57, 0.560
	1308364	32.5	32.396	
	1319410	32.5	32.669	

100	2612887	65.00	64.696	100.2 ± 0.57, 0.570
	2636218	65.00	65.274	
	2640982	65.00	65.392	
150	3934511	97.5	97.42	100.3 ± 0.41, 0.410
	3952322	97.5	97.861	
	3966740	97.5	98.218	

B

Level (%)	Sample peak area	Amount of standard added (mg)	Amount recovered	% Recovery ± SD, %RSD (n = 3)
50	201563	5	4.991	99.8 ± 0.48, 0.480
	200415	5	4.962	
	202315	5	5.009	
100	402896	10	10.0	99.9 ± 0.53, 0.530
	401442	10	9.939	
	405653	10	10.044	
150	603204	15	14.935	99.7 ± 0.53, 0.530
	601154	15	14.884	
	607451	15	15.04	

3.5 Precision: In method precision study prepare six different sample solutions in the concentration of Paracetamol (20µg/ml) and Diclofenac Sodium (60 µg/ml) were injected into HPLC system. The % assay results were found to be in range of 98% to 102%. Peak areas were calculated, which were used to calculate mean, SD and %RSD values. These results are given below table 4.

Table 4: Intraday precision results

S.No	Paracetamol			Diclofenac Sodium		
	Conc. (µg/ml)	Area	% assay	Conc. (µg/ml)	Area	% assay
1	650	2611541	99.5	100	402659	99.7
2		2643185	100.7		400021	99
3		2638161	100.5		401555	99.4
4		2627535	100.1		404331	100.1
5		2654774	101.1		402063	99.5
6		2641283	100.6		398728	98.7

Fig. 5: Chromatogram of method precision

3.6 Intermediate precision: Separate instruments were used on different days, in different locations, for independent investigations into six different replicates of the sample solution. Mean, RSD values have been calculated and determined from the peak regions. The following table shows the results. Paracetamol (650 μ g/ml) and Diclofenac Sodium (100 μ g/ml) was analyzed on 2 different days with 6 different samples. Thus, it has been found that the current method yields very accurate results, with RSD values less than 2 percent and percent assay values near 100 percent. In table 5 we can see the results.

Table 5: Inter-day outcomes

S. No	Paracetamol		Diclofenac Sodium	
	Area counts	% assay	Area counts	% assay
1	2638065	100.5	402596	99.7
2	2625198	100.0	404493	100.1
3	2616315	99.7	400204	99.1
4	2641422	100.6	398633	98.7
5	2612944	99.5	399512	98.9
6	2652887	101.0	401024	99.3

3.7 LOD and LOQ: The LOD concentration of Paracetamol was 1.95 μ g/ml and s/n values is 3 and Diclofenac Sodium was 0.3 μ g/ml and s/n values is 3. The LOQ concentration for Paracetamol was 6.5 μ g/ml and their s/n values are 10, and Diclofenac Sodium was 1.0 μ g/ml and s/n values is 10. The method is validated as per the ICH guidelines.

Table 6: LOD and LOQ Results

Paracetamol				Diclofenac Sodium			
LOD		LOQ		LOD		LOQ	
Concentration	s/n	Concentration	s/n	concentration	s/n	Concentration	s/n
1.95 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	3	6.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10	0.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	3	1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10

B**Fig. 6: Chromatogram of (A) LOD and (B) LOQ**

3.8 Robustness: The design of the experiment was intentionally altered in order to test the robustness of the system. Examples of such changes include changing the flow rate, organic to inorganic ratio, and so on. The results were robust and tabulated in Table 7.

Table 7: Robustness data of Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium

Title of the Parameter	% RSD	
	Paracetamol	Diclofenac Sodium
Flow Minus (0.9 ml/min)	0.72	0.90
Flow Plus (1.1 ml/min)	0.70	0.27
Organic Minus (18:82)	0.72	0.65
Organic Plus (22:78)	0.46	0.15

3.9 Degradation studies: Partial degradation of the drug was accomplished using various forced degradation conditions on the Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium sample. Research has been carried out to see if the method works for degrading products. Additionally, the studies describe the conditions under which the drug is unstable, providing further information so that appropriate precautions are taken during the process of formulation in order to avoid possible instabilities.

Acid degradation: 84.8 mg of sample was moved to a volumetric flask of 10 ml, add 1 ml of 1N HCl and left it for 15 min. After 15 min add 1 ml of 1N NaOH and make up to the diluent mark. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Filter the solution using syringe filter and injected into HPLC system.

Alkali degradation: 84.8 mg of sample was moved to a volumetric flask of 10 ml, add 1 ml of 1N NaOH and left it for 15 min. After 15 min add 1 ml of 1N HCl and make up to the mark. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Filter the solution using syringe filter and injected into HPLC system.

Peroxide degradation: 84.8 mg of sample was moved to a volumetric flask of 10 ml, add 1 ml of 10% hydrogen peroxide solution and make up to the mark with diluents. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Filter the solution using syringe filter and injected into HPLC system.

Reduction degradation: 84.8 mg of sample was moved to a volumetric flask of 10 ml and add 1 ml of 10% sodium bi sulphite solution and make up to the mark with diluents. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Filter the solution using syringe filter and injected into HPLC system.

Thermal degradation: The standards were set in an oven at 105°C for 6 hrs. By using these standards standard solution was prepared and injected into HPLC system.

Hydrolysis degradation: 84.8 mg of sample was moved to a volumetric flask of 10 ml and add 1 ml of HPLC grade water and make up to the mark with diluents. Further dilute 1 ml to 10 ml with diluents. Filter the solution using syringe filter and injected into HPLC system.

Photo degradation: 100 mg of sample was set in photo stability chamber for 24 hrs. The resultant solution was injected into HPLC system.

The results of forced degradation were shown in table 8.

Table 8: Results of forced degradation

Degradation condition	Paracetamol		Diclofenac Sodium	
	% Assay	% Deg	% Assay	% Deg
Control degradation	100	0	100	0
Acid degradation	97.5	2.5	95.5	4.5
Alkali degradation	89.7	10.3	88.5	11.5
Oxidation degradation	86.4	13.6	86.4	13.6
Reduction degradation	99.3	0.7	97.9	2.1
Thermal degradation	92.3	7.7	99.3	0.7
Photolytic degradation	99.6	0.4	98.4	1.6
Hydrolysis degradation	88.9	11.1	98.2	1.8

4. CONCLUSION

The developed method was accurate, precise and reliable for the simultaneous analysis of Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium in pharmaceutical formulations. This method was validated for linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, forced degradation of Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium. The RSD values for all parameters were found to be less 2, which indicates the validity of method and results obtained by this method are in fair agreement. Finally this method can be used for better analysis of Paracetamol and Diclofenac Sodium.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST: None

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